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Deciphering the Dynamics between Naïve Nataraj and Vicious Vasu in R. K. Narayan's *The Man-eater of Malgudi*

Dr. Amitava Pal

Assistant Professor of English,
East Calcutta Girls' College,
Lake Town, Kolkata.

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Abstract:

R. K. Narayan's acclaimed novel *The Man-eater of Malgudi* (1961) foregrounds the conflict between the simple Nataraj and the predatory, profit-making, power-hungry Vasu. The relationship between the two is conventionally viewed as a straightforward battle between good and evil, presented with a mythological flavour. However, this paper argues that the relationship between Nataraj and Vasu is not as unidimensional as it seems. It is true that Nataraj fights heart and soul with his limited ability against Vasu's overwhelming dominance. He is relieved when Vasu eventually brings about his own destruction. However, the novel also occasionally shows Nataraj's reluctant admiration towards Vasu's direct, determined and dogged pursuit of power and money. Nataraj condemns Vasu's Machiavellian and corrupt method, but his confrontation with Vasu makes him wiser. He recognises the need to overcome his own naivete and stir up his own courage. It is a conflict which offers Nataraj multiple lessons.

Keywords: predatory, self-destruction, mythological, multidimensional.

Introduction:

The town of Malgudi is synonymous with R K Narayan. This fictitious town remains imprinted in the Indian literary landscape with an unflinching fascination. This small South Indian town plays host to yet another enthralling narrative as Narayan takes up his pen for his ninth novel *The Man-eater of Malgudi* (1961). The title of the novel may bring to the reader's mind the title of Jim Corbett's famous 1944 book *Man-Eaters of Kumaon*. However, the 'Man-Eater' in the title of Narayan's novel does not refer to any cannibal or fierce animal. The epithet is metaphorical and suggestive, reflecting the over-bearing and soul-crushing quality of the novel's antagonist.

Malgudi represents an organic way of life, in harmony with the flow of nature. The palmyra tree presides as a reigning deity over the bathing ghats. However, this serenity of Malgudi is perturbed by the advent of Vasu, the 'man-eater' of the novel's title. Vasu exploits the vulnerabilities of the novel's protagonist-cum-narrator Nataraj. Nataraj appears as a simple and naïve fellow who is no match for the vicious Vasu. While the relation between Nataraj and Vasu has mostly been viewed as a battle between good and evil, this paper would argue that their relation is not so unidimensional. It is far more complex and layered than it seems at first sight.

The protagonist of the story is a rather meek and unheroic Nataraj, who begins his first-person narration: "I could have profitably rented out the little room in front of my press. On Market Road, with a view of the fountain, it was coveted by every would-be shopkeeper in our town" (Narayan 1). The very opening sentence makes it clear that the narrator-cum-protagonist Nataraj is not good at making profits; neither does he intend to. Malgudi in this opening section of the novel carries within it vestiges of different religions. Nataraj has unflinching faith in the blessings of Goddess Laxmi and adorns his press with a framed picture of the goddess. He takes holy dips in the river every morning as the sun shoots its first crimson rays. He takes pride in his wife

'continuing the traditions of our ancient home in Kabir Street' (Narayan 1). At the same time, he embraces western education and sends his son to Albert Mission School. Through goddess Laxmi, Albert Mission School and Kabir Street, the Indian ethos of co-existences and synthesis of diverse religions are etched out in the very opening pages. The religious fervour is not just a matter of occasional reverence; it is integral to the ethos of Malgudi. It is this religious spirit which will come to the foreground towards the end of the novel.

To the humble Nataraj can be contrasted the alien aggressor Vasu who forcibly imposes himself upon Nataraj. The introductory description of Vasu's countenance holds a clue to his hideous nature and visceral aggression- "a tanned face, large powerful eyes under thick eyebrows, large forehead and a shock of unkempt hair over it, like a black halo" (Narayan 10). No less hideous is his philosophy: "After all, we are civilized human beings, educated and cultured, and it is up to us to prove our superiority to nature." (Narayan 13) This erroneous philosophy is the cornerstone of Vasu's trampling of nature and natural life. His false sense of man's superiority to nature endangers the hitherto maintained equilibrium between man's need and nature's bounty.

Vasu boasts of his over-weening brute physical strength: 'I could also snap chains, twist iron bars, and pulverize granite '. (Narayan 14) His philosophy is '*veer-bhogya vasundhara*' -- 'Science conquers nature in a new way each day; why not in creation also?' (Narayan 13) Making money is his motto, and Malgudi to him is a 'miserable little place' (Narayan 14) where he has come to make some more money. The novelist calls Vasu 'the man-eater'. However, noticeably, Vasu is a taxidermist and it is he who kills and stuffs the animals. The author's obvious suggestion is that Vasu is as fierce as predatory animals, and his brute quality subdues Nataraj and other Malgudians. Vasu claims as his victims both animals and human beings. He embodies an all-encompassing greed and utmost disregard for nature and environment.

Although his name is Nataraj, the central character lacks the destructive and creative forces of the mythological Nataraj. He cannot cleanse his own press of the pernicious visitant named Vasu. Nataraj looks on with impotent rage as his native place becomes the underbelly where the cherished ideal of ahimsa receives a death-blow: "I was brought up in a house where we were taught never to kill. When we swatted flies, we had to do it without the knowledge of our elders." (Narayan 53) And now he is confronted by a man who kills tigers for profit.

There is a method in Vasu's madness. He is hand-in-glove with forest-officers who know and number every beast in the forest. He brings a forest-officer and tells about him: "He knows and has numbered every beast that's there" (Narayan 25). Vasu has a tendency to assert man's megalomaniac power over nature. 'Knowing' and 'numbering' become for Vasu another way of establishing man's commercial grip over nature. Beasts are to be known and numbered to be slaughtered and stuffed. For Vasu, the modus operandi is his nefarious nexus with forest-officials. He decimates wildlife with tacit support from those who are supposed to protect it.

Published barely a decade after Independence, the novel also becomes a critique of the then Indian nation-state which was still struggling to get its acts together. Nataraj's journalist-friend connects this Vasu-phenomenon with the larger problems facing the country: "Why do you tolerate these things? As a nation, we are what we are today because of our lack of positive grip over our affairs." (Narayan 54) The novel repeatedly shows how Malgudi is yet to fully realise the meaning of freedom and often views it through a narrow prism.

Vasu has all the tricks under his sleeves. He exploits legal loopholes and drags Nataraj to court, alleging that Nataraj has forcefully tried to evict him. Nataraj, on his part, struggles to convince other people, including the adjournment lawyer, that he did not willingly rent the room to Vasu, and instead it was Vasu who had taken control of the room with guile and force. The

traditional Indian community, despite all its strengths, remains as aloof as it could be during these troubled days, and Nataraj has to fight this David-Goliath fight alone. Nataraj now finds himself ensnared in a legal tangle. It is also a criticism of the convoluted judicial processes of our country which largely retained the colonial laws and procedures in all their complexities.

Nataraj's troubles proliferate as the neighbours complain against him for allowing tanning and curing of skins in residential area. This is the constant irony. Nataraj never gets any official or local support when he tries to take on Vasu. However, the same administration and neighbours turn against him when the consequences of Vasu's misdeeds make themselves felt. Nataraj, despite all his efforts, comes across as a co-accomplice in Vasu's horrendous acts. Nataraj is crushed in a conflict in which he never was a party.

At the simplest level, the conflict between Nataraj and Vasu is a battle between good and evil forces. However, the relationship between Nataraj and Vasu is not so unidimensional. It is true that Nataraj resents the presence of Vasu in his press. However, there are also moments when Nataraj rather reluctantly or even unwittingly praises Vasu's attitude. George Woodcock, in his discussion of Narayan, finds here a reflection of the contemporary Indian mindset. In the essay “Two Great Commonwealth Novelists: R. K. Narayan and V. S. Naipaul”, Woodcock writes: “The sickness from which all the citizens of Malgudi suffer, and which their mediocrity reflects, is the mid-twentieth-century alienation of the Indian middle class.” (Woodcock 18) In Woodcock’s view, Vasu symbolises a material western model which the Malgudians cannot fully comprehend.

The conflict between Vasu and Nataraj has indeed often been viewed as a conflict between modernity and tradition. It is true that Nataraj clings on to tradition. The Heidelberg machine is an instrument of modernity that Nataraj is happy to see in his neighbour's shop, but he himself never aspires to have one. He believes in his good old way that camaraderie, and not Heidelberg, is key

to success in a small-scale business like his. Towards the end of the novel, Nataraja himself has this same realisation: "The matter with me was that I was not able to say "no" to anyone, and that got me into complications with everyone from a temple prostitute to a taxidermist." (Narayan 137) He was paying a high price for being the nice guy; for having failed to put up any determined resistance. M. K. Naik opines in the article "Theme and Form in R. K. Narayan's *The Man-eater of Malgudi*", "The interplay between Vasu and Nataraj also indicates a contrast between two diametrically opposed attitudes to life...between the demonical self-centred egotism of Vasu and the ineffectual self-effacing altruism of Nataraj." (Naik 68)

Vasu imports an altogether new rule of game. V P Rao opines in his essay "The Art of R. K. Narayan": "Vasu is the catalyst of change in this orthodox little world. For Narayan the impact of modernity...is symbolized by the disruption of the privacy of the press's interior, separated from the outside world by the blue curtain of Innocence." (Rao 32) Mr. Rao further writes about Vasu: "His Americanisms and his aggressiveness, like his business, are totally alien to Malgudi. He is the apostle of science and modernity and hates sentiment." (Rao 34) However, one wonders whether these qualities are more Machiavellian than modern. One needs to ask whether the kind of modernity Vasu represents is really what one must look for. Despite Vasu's semblances of an artist, he is more of an out-and-out capitalist who runs over Malgudi and Mempi for monetary profits. Viewed from today's scenario, Vasu pre-figures the various land-grabbing corporates who plunder local resources for making exponential profit.

Vasu becomes a public enemy only when he sets his eyes on the temple-elephant Kumar. It is religious fervour that collapses narrow divisions and galvanizes local support against Vasu. Religious faith acts as the glue which brings the town together. It is Rangī, the temple-prostitute, who acts as a catalyst, revealing Vasu's plan of shooting the elephant on the day of the poet's book-

release programme and festival. The novel now reaches a climactic point. Nataraj also becomes pro-active since it is not any ordinary elephant, but the temple-elephant. Religion and mythology provide a force which a mere awareness of the wildlife never could. Nataraj says with real indignation, "It was impossible to conceive of Kumar's being dissected and stuffed and serving as an umbrella stand or wastebasket in some fashionable home in the Eastern or Western world." (Narayan 146) This realisation stirs some heroic qualities in Nataraj. After remaining largely inactive for the greater part of the crucial day -- the day of the procession, he strives to shed his anti-hero persona, and stealthily visits Vasu's den at the dead of night to prevent Vasu from shooting the sacred elephant. The novel now assumes an element of suspense. Although Nataraj gets hold of Vasu's gun, he is too afraid to fight him. Nataraj in his timidity gives an ironic and practical twist to Gandhi's philosophy, "Nonviolence would be the safest policy with him. Mahatma Gandhi was right in asking people to carry on their fight with the weapon of non-violence; the chances of getting hurt were less in this process." (Narayan 154)

However, eventually it turns out to be much ado about nothing. Vasu is too deep in a sleep to disrupt the procession. However, the relief proves to be short-lived. The next morning Vasu is discovered dead in his room. "Vasu dead proved a greater nuisance than Vasu alive." (Narayan 182) This is the irony of Indian police and legal system. It is largely ineffective when it is to play its part, and overtly active when it should be muted.

Now the story becomes a 'whodunnit'? The primary investigation suggests: "Mr. Vasu of Junagadh died of a concussion received on the frontal bone at the right temple, delivered by a blunt instrument." (Narayan 186) Suspicions and insidious observations fly quick and fast. A brass vessel appears to be the potential instrument. Nataraj in his own way connects the dots and considers Rangī to be the assassin. Meanwhile, many others, including his wife, view him as the

agent. To her, this act becomes for Nataraj a badge of honour: 'you have killed a rakshasa single-handed!' (Narayan 189) In any case, the association of Nataraj's press with a murder tarnishes Nataraj's image: "This was the greatest act of destruction that the Man-Eater had performed, destroying my name, my friendships, and my world." (Narayan 192) Nataraj is eventually redeemed after Rangi gives a detailed account of the sequences leading to Vasu's death. It is amazingly concluded that Vasu had accidentally slapped himself dead.

Narayan brings a mythological flavour to the novel. Early in the novel, Sastri establishes a mythological parallel to illustrate the conflict between good and evil. He narrates: "Every demon appears in the world with a special boon of indestructibility. Yet the universe has survived all the rakshasas that were ever born. Every demon carries within him, unknown to himself, a tiny seed of self-destruction." (Narayan 77) Sastri elaborates the qualities of a Rakshasa and associates Vasu with the Rakshasa figure. Sastri narrates: "Every rakshasa gets swollen with his ego. He thinks he is invincible, beyond every law. But sooner or later something or other will destroy him." (Narayan 78) Sastri first recounts the story of Ravana: "There was Ravana, the protagonist in Ramayana, who had ten heads and twenty arms ... The earth shook under his tyranny. Still he came to a sad end." (Narayan 78) Sastri does not stop here. He gives a long list of demons who eventually were destroyed. Sastri's words prove prophetic as Vasu also brings about his own death.

Even when Vasu is at the height of his power, Sastri has the conviction that his tyranny will come to an end. He narrates the story of Bhasmasura who initially appeared invincible. But even Bhasmasura could not escape his doom. Sastri says: "Then there was Bhasmasura, who acquired a special boon that everything he touched should be scorched, while nothing could ever destroy him" (Narayan 79) In a cunning way, the gods put an end to Bhasmasura's life: "God Vishnu was incarnated as a dancer of great beauty, named Mohini, with whom the asura became

infatuated. At one point of the dance Mohini placed her palms on her own head, and the demon followed this gesture in complete forgetfulness and was reduced to ashes." (Narayan 79) Sastri stands vindicated at the end of the novel, as Vasu accidentally kills himself.

Narayan's story may be reassuring in suggesting that every evil contains within it the seed for destruction. However, it reveals the utter inefficiency of the administration and legal system that people have to depend upon the self-destructiveness of the evil and people have little power in curbing the evil themselves. Bala Kothandaraman rightly points out that a "series of fortuitous events, and not the efforts of the protagonist, restore the disrupted order in a Narayan novel" (Kothandaraman 31).

Malgudi survives Vasu's reign of terror. Its forests and wildlife overcome the alien predator. And the novel ends with the resumption of the tag-team printing partnership between Nataraj and Sastri. Malgudi gradually limps back to its normalcy. Edwin Gerow finds in 'Narayan's fictive world' 'a circular pattern of Order-Disruption-Restoration of Order' (Gerow 12). Although Malgudi's brush with the middle-aged man-eater does not trigger any radical transformation, it leaves Nataraj a wiser person -- a person with better grasp of his strengths and weaknesses, of moral values and decisive actions. He recognises the need to cultivate courage, capacity and maturity to fight an evil force. The conflict with Vasu also gives him a glimpse of vile ambition and dark potential of human beings.

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